

Research Report

Planning a Pilot Telemedicine Service for a Remote Area

Medical Clinic: A Primer for Industrial Projects

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Title Change Note: Changed from [Pilot Telemedicine Service for a Remote Area Medical Clinic] to [Planning a Pilot Telemedicine Service for a Remote Area Medical Clinic: A Primer for Industrial Projects]. This in the Author's opinion, more appropriately describes the unaltered content.

Abstract

Medical clinics operating in remote areas, face the dilemma of whether to treat patients at location, or recommend urgent or emergency evacuation. Depending on the environment, project and work particulars, personnel may report with myriad signs and symptoms. This is often compounded by the medical history, or a less than desirable predeployment medical screening. Telemedicine can provide a partial or supplementary solution, that can address several issues. Implemented and delivered in an optimum way, it can prevent unnecessary evacuation, save the project expenses, and relieve receiving healthcare institutions from undue burden. The author is proposing a pilot telemedicine service(TMS) that can be implemented on a trial basis, and then evaluated as to endpoints and parameters achieved. This will give stakeholders, an idea as how TMS can contribute, to overall objectives of medical care, delivered with resource constraints in mind.

Keywords: remote, trauma, satellite, CPR, EMR, stakeholders, community.

Pilot Telemedicine Study for a Remote Area Medical Clinic

Telemedicine is emerging as a vital cog, in healthcare delivery to underserved and resource poor locations. The success of normalisation of TMS, depends on execution of a thoughtfully designed implementation plan. To prevent early allocation of full resources, the author is proposing a pilot implementation of the service, targeting one or more common clinical conditions, that could benefit, with the initiation of TMS.

Pilot Service Implementation Plan^{1 2}

This pilot service, is meant specifically for initiation of TMS at the Camp Clinic(CC) of the Mineral Extraction and Processing Project(MEPP), but can be modified to support implementation design for any remote area site clinic, after taking into consideration, the work environment, logistical issues, project, and work particulars. The CC remains in the vicinity of the project site, and caters to both on-duty and resting personnel. The TMS remains accessible to nearby communities, who are not part of the workforce, for any medical emergencies.

Background^{3 4}

The MEPP operates in Eastern Africa. The project location remains subject to extreme heat, throughout the summer months and beyond. Both local and expatriates are employed in the project. Various types of acute and chronic cases report to the camp clinic. The regional community hospital(RCH), located in the district town, is 4 hours by road, and the nearest primary health center(PHC) is 2 hours from the clinic. The road is varied, including rocky surfaces, high altitude crossing, and tarmac paving towards the town side. Site medics, may find it useful to avail telemedicine services, for a range of medical conditions, and surely benefit from the free TMS being provided by the emergency department at RCH(runs on grants from international aid organisations).

Clinical Scenario⁵

Trauma remains a major concern, due to the nature of work. During two years of operation, the clinic has received cases with blunt trauma, chemical injuries, unconsciousness, lacerations, etc. The required management of these cases can range from basic first aid, to complex life sustaining interventions. The myriad ways major trauma cases can present include, low GCS, major lacerations, airway compromise, compound fractures, extensive burns, avulsions, amputations, etc. The patient may rapidly begin to deteriorate and go into cardiorespiratory arrest.

Needs assessment

On several occasions, the CC has received patients with major trauma. The primary goal of patient stabilisation and intervention protocols using the ATLS algorithms, have been used in case management. The distance and nature of roads, between the CC and RCH, makes the transfer of patients an arduous and risky task. The stakeholders are planning further expansion of the project, with mining operations to be increased both in scale and complexity. The built environment to undergo structural changes to include advance machinery and other equipment. It is proposed, that the stakeholders implement a pilot trauma telemedicine program, to evaluate, how TMS can affect project viability and enhance patient care. As coronavirus 19 epidemic puts pressure on the regional healthcare institutes, there is the possibility of enhanced and equitable care using the TMS service. The RCH hosts a provider TMS, that covers trauma, and has a general emergency department, and can be used as the nodal referral destination, both for telemedicine sessions, and for physical transfers.

Site Survey

Communications: The MEPP accesses the internet via satellite and the CC remains included in the grid. Satellite broadband has been functional for over one year, at the time of this pilot study. Cell phone towers have been provided in the project operating area, and mobile phones work most of the time. There is also the option of two way radio transponders, available to all key personnel. There is a single satellite phone available at the project office.

Power and backup: The electric power source is by diesel generators, operating on 12 hours rotating shifts. All electrical, electronic and digital equipment remain connected to the grid, except for a 10 minutes of transition period, when the generators are changed, every 12 hours.

Local support: Rural communities are plagued by illiteracy and poverty, and remain skeptical of the service. Further interventions, as regards to education, orientation and awareness needs to be performed under the aegis of the regional and federal government. Community leaders are better educated, and can appraise the service critically.

Technology: Section offices have desktop PCs installed, which regularly connect to the internet. Current ICT standards are maintained in the project operating areas, and technical resources and expertise is available from the district town. Advanced and complex equipment and tools can be sourced from the federal capital.

Logistics: Vehicles for ration, supplies and other requirements, are scheduled for departure and arrival once a week. There are provisions for emergency dispatch using daily goods vehicle.

Repair and maintenance: IT technician is not available at site. For any repair or maintenance technicians can be contacted over email, and onsite service requested. Response time is 4 hours.

Electrical technician and maintenance staff remain available round the clock. The district town has an airport meant for travel within the country and can reach the federal capital in 75 minutes.

TELEMEDICINE PILOT
TMS dataflow

TELEMEDICINE PILOT
TMS Tehcnical Specifications^{6 7 8 9}

Telemedicine Services pilot	Specifications	Compliance/Standards	Backup/Alternative/Scaling
Network			
Internet	Satellite Broadband GEO		Satellite LEO; 4G tower
	Dedicate channel with 50-100 Mbps		Wi-max
	Leased line; Ku band (14/12 Ghz)	latency 200 ms	
Server	NA		Telemedicine Server
Telemedicine live videoconferencing	HD H.323(8mbps) 8K uhd (OpenH264)	H.264	Desktop Telemedicine, or
	Dedicated hardware platform		DVTS (30mbps)
	1920/1080 pixels		720/480
	Encryption	AES/RSA	Encryption IPsec, or
	SVC		Desktop H.264 software.
Medical Camera	If required by provider site		
Telemedicine Workstation (Client)		CE FCC part 15	
Desktop PC	Standard 5th generation processor	Minimum 2 Ghz	

	Integrated graphics; network interface card		Dedicated graphics card
	4GB RAM		
	Hard Disk	1 Terabyte	
	Industrial grade keyboard		
	Wall mounted dual Monitor 17" each; HD		
	ports to connect peripherals; headset;		
	UPS; standard PSU		
	Biomedical peripherals; stethoscope, dermoscope,	Class I FDA MDDS	Additional sets
	ophthalmoscope, POCUS		
Integrated peripherals	Modem with Router with LAN and Wi-Fi		
Bedside	Patient monitor	HL7/wi-fi	
	NIBP, pulse wave, SpO2, breathing pattern, rate, ECG		Additional sets
Software	Windows 10/11		Linux (Ubuntu/Mate)
Software	Open-source Computerised Patient Record/EMR		
	Integrated PACS	DICOM	
	Encryption(desktop/server)		

	Patient monitoring data integration		
	Telemedicine integration		
	Biomedical data integration		
	Desktop telemedicine	For emergency	

Technical issues

1. Outside temperatures, are among the highest, that can be found anywhere in the world. All indoor locations, are airconditioned.
2. Internet communication is only available via satellite.
3. Electrical power remains off for 10 minutes, two times a day.
4. Selected stock of IT equipment relevant to TMS, to be kept at site. Offsite IT technician will maintain list, and access stock when required.
5. Site Medics to maintain selected stock of biomedical equipment relevant to TMS.

Legal, organisational, social and cultural issues^{10 11 12 13}

1. Requisite permissions needed to be acquired from relevant ministries, and designated departments.
2. Site medics must have proof of credentialing and primary source verification. Additional qualification and certifications may be required. Provider site, should provide the camp clinic with the above specifications of healthcare staff, who are going to provide telemedicine services.
3. Referring medic remains liable for the patient.

4. Community leaders and educated personnel perceive the advantages of timely assistance, and access to specialists. They remain appreciative of the immediate feedback received over TMS. Other personnel generally remain resistant.
5. All personnel remained apprehensive, regarding the quality of care, accuracy of diagnosis, privacy and confidentiality issues. The absence of the physician at location, remained a concern for all.
6. Language remains a major barrier while accessing resources regarding training, awareness and orientation.
7. Organisational stakeholders remain hopeful of the positive impact, TMS can have in complex clinical situations.

Cost and benefits

	Costs	Benefits
Pilot	Electrical grid power	Reduced evacuation incidents.
	Satellite broadband subscription and data transfer costs	Timely access to expert opinion and feedback.
	Staff training and maintenance	Case follow-up frequency increase.
	Videoconferencing hardware	Reduced hospital visits.
	Desktop PC and peripherals	Reduced cross-infection.
	Peripheral and wireless biomedical devices	Increased access to specialists.
	Patient monitor	
	Setup costs	
	Annual maintenance contracts	
	Software systems and packages	
	Contract with provider site(nil)	
	Acquiring requisite licenses and permits.	
	Community and project personnel orientation.	

Implementation Plan¹⁴

1. Plan discussed with project stakeholders. Authorisation letter received.
2. Stakeholders/CC to sign initial agreement with provider site at RCH. Guidelines, standards and policies, if any received.

3. Rules and regulations confirmed from ministry website. All requisite licenses and permits to be at hand.
4. Technical requirements discussed with infrastructure providers, including installation, setup, repair, maintenance and support.
5. Designated CC personnel sent to provider site for orientation and training.
6. Contract signed with vendors.
7. Testing begins, once setup is complete and vendor arranges for initial orientation.

Testing

1. Test desktop teleconferencing ability to receive and record audiovisual data. Test supporting software(CPR/EMR; PACS), for ability to receive and archive data.
2. Test patient monitor and connected peripherals, are able to measure and transmit data to EMR/desktop telemedicine suite.
3. Test peripheral biomedical equipment,are able to measure and transmit data to EMR/desktop telemedicine suite.
4. Test reserve power supply(UPS), can sustain operations for 10 minutes, during generator phase change.
5. Mock drill to address originating site healthcare and support staff readiness.
6. Test dedicated teleconferencing platform, with regards to audiovisual quality.
7. Request mock teletrauma session with provider site; all three platforms, viz dedicated teleconferencing, desktop teleconferencing and software systems(DCR/EMR/telemedicine suite), to be tested.

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